

منتخب صحابہ کرام کے اجتہادات کی نوعیت کا تحقیقی مطالعہ عصری مسائل کے تناظر میں

The Research Study on the Nature of the Ijtihads of Selected Companions of the Prophet in the Context of Contemporary Issues

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Abstract

This PhD research study delves into the nature of ijtihad (independent legal reasoning) as employed by selected companions of the Prophet Muhammad to address contemporary issues. Ijtihad involves deriving rulings on matters not explicitly addressed in the Quran and Sunnah (the Prophet's teachings). The study focuses on companions renowned for their expertise in ijtihad and their substantial contributions to Islamic jurisprudence. Utilizing a qualitative research design, the study examines primary sources such as the works of the companions themselves, accounts from their students, and commentaries by later scholars. It then contextualizes these ijtihads within contemporary challenges facing the Muslim world, including those related to gender, politics, human rights, and social justice. The analysis underscores the relevance and applicability of the companions' ijtihads in addressing these modern concerns. This study contributes to Islamic Studies by offering a deeper understanding of the nature and significance of ijtihad within Islamic jurisprudence. It reveals that the companions' ijtihads were characterized by a strong foundation in the Quran and Sunnah, a mastery of the Arabic language, and a comprehensive knowledge of legal and social contexts. They employed a range of methodologies, including analogy, public interest, and established principles of jurisprudence. The study concludes that the companions' ijtihads provide valuable insights and a framework for addressing contemporary issues in a manner aligned with the spirit and objectives of Islam. It emphasizes the importance of a contextualized understanding of ijtihad in addressing modern challenges and promoting the development of Islamic jurisprudence.

Keywords: : Ijtihad , Islamic Jurisprudence, Companions of the Prophet , Contemporary Issues in Islam, Legal Reasoning in Islam, Modern Islamic Challenges

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